

Content Mastering Services in Efforts to Improve Student's Confidence

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Abstract: As prospective guidance and counseling teachers, students of the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education are required to have the ability to speak in public, especially in front of the class together with students when conducting counseling services. This study aims to look at content services to be able to increase student confidence, especially in the third semester. In this study, the research design used was a qualitative method (Sugiyono, 2008) explaining that qualitative itself is a research based on post-positivism philosophy, the research is intended to examine objects that are natural, in this study experiment is the opposite and the researcher himself is the key instrument. Data collection techniques in qualitative, data analysis itself is inductive/qualitative. The results of qualitative research itself emphasize more on meaning than generalization, the data collection method used uses primary data sources and secondary data sources. Through this study, it was found that the efforts made to increase self-confidence through content mastery services were able to significantly increase student confidence.

Keywords: Content Mastery Service, Increase, Confidence

I. Introduction

Building self-confidence in each individual is not easy, even though self-confidence is the main key for individuals to be successful in various fields. Individuals themselves are said to have low self-confidence when they have difficulty speaking in front of the audience until finally they also have difficulty conveying their ideas in front of many people. Individuals who have low levels of self-confidence will experience doubts about their beliefs in their own abilities, have negative feelings towards themselves and have weak beliefs about their potential (Hasanah and Saugi, 2021). As a teacher educator is a determining factor for success in learning achievement, teachers are expected to be able to master skills confidently in front of the class, this of course also applies to education students who are likely to become teachers in the future. As a teacher or educator, the teacher is one of the determining factors for the success of any educational effort. Therefore, a teacher is required to be able to know and understand the principles of learning and be able to master class conditions at the time of teaching. Building self-confidence in students is not an easy thing, a teacher should first have good self-confidence in order to help the students' confidence in class. Self-confidence is a person's belief in all aspects

of the advantages he has, this belief makes him feel able to achieve various goals in his life (Bidjuni, 2016). Various efforts have been made by educators in order to build self-confidence, self-confidence is basically the ability that a person has, which creates firmness or confidence to act in a wider area (Tamelab, Ngongo, and Oetpah, 2021). A person needs self-confidence to succeed in his life because self-confidence plays a role in encouraging and motivating a person to react appropriately to challenges and opportunities that come his way and to feel various happiness in his life.

As prospective teachers, students of the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education are required to have the ability to speak in public, especially in front of the class together with students when conducting counseling services. The ability of students to speak in public mostly uses group discussion and presentation methods, students often feel anxious to express their thoughts orally, either during group discussions, when asking questions to the lecturer, or when they have to speak in front of the class when presenting assignments. Low self-confidence in students can be seen clearly, this condition is characterized by a fear of showing performance and interactional situations with other people and these conditions have an impact on the quality of individual life, affecting social functions and relationships with the community (Febriana, Dwityanto, and Psi, 2016). Several factors that cause anxiety in public speaking tend to cause the individual concerned to record in his subconscious mind both visually, auditory, kinesthetically, as well as things that have an impact on his confidence when speaking in public. Low self-confidence is also characterized by high anxiety, this individual tends to shut down and is generally accompanied by avoidance behavior because he cannot stand the criticism he may receive, this is often associated with excessive fear that others will judge him (Nainggolan, 2011). But increasing self-confidence is not an ability that comes by itself, but must be trained. Belief in oneself is important for one's mental health. Low self-confidence is feared to hinder achieving personal and professional success and happiness. This study aims to look at content services to be able to increase student confidence, especially in the third semester.

II. Theoretical Study

Content Mastery Service

Content mastery service is one of the services in guidance and counseling that aims to enable individuals to master certain aspects of content synergistically (Maryanto, Setyowani, & Mugiarto, 2013). Content mastery services are services in guidance and counseling to help students master certain content, especially competence and or habits in doing, doing or doing something useful in life at school/madrasah, family, and community in accordance with the demands of progress and intelligent character that commendable, according to his potential and interests (Gutara, Rangka, & Prasetyaningtyas, 2017). Content mastery services are assistance services to individuals or groups to master certain abilities or competencies through student learning activities (Prayitno, 2012). In his research (Hasanah, Ahmad, & Karneli, 2017) found that the importance of content mastery services was able to increase student learning concentration and the teaching and learning process in the classroom.

Content Mastery Service Purpose

The purpose of the content mastery service (Maidah, 2021) is for students to master aspects of content, both

abilities and certain competencies in an integrated manner. By mastering content students gain broad insight and understanding, directing judgments and attitudes, mastering certain ways, in order to meet needs and overcome problems. Content mastery services aim to assist individuals (alone or in groups) to master certain abilities or competencies through learning activities, with content mastery, individuals are expected to be able to meet their needs and overcome the problems they experience (Prayitno, 2004). Different opinions were expressed about the purpose of the content mastery service in the field of learning activity development, the mastery service aims to add insight and understanding, direct judgment and attitudes, master learning ways or habits and improve learning skills, and overcome learning problems (Adiningtyas, 2016).

Confidence

Self-confidence is basically born from the awareness that if you decide to do something, then something must also be done, self-confidence is present in the individual in the belief that the individual has the determination to do anything, until the goal he wants is achieved (Ifdil, Denich, & Ilyas, 2017). Through an attitude of self-acceptance that can reflect a sense of pleasure in connection with the reality of oneself, individuals who are satisfied with their quality will tend to feel safe, not disappointed and know what they need, so they can be independent and not dependent on others in deciding everything objectively (Fitri, Zola, & Ifdil, 2018). Self-confidence is an attitude or belief in one's own abilities, individuals become less anxious, feel free to carry out activities comfortably and responsibly, are polite in interacting with others, have motivation, accept their own strengths and weaknesses (Tanjung & Amelia, 2017).

III. Methodology

In this study, the research design used was a qualitative method (Sugiyono, 2008) explaining that qualitative itself is a research based on post-positivism philosophy, the research is intended to examine objects that are natural, in this study experiment is the opposite and the researcher himself is the key instrument. Data collection techniques in qualitative, data analysis itself is inductive/qualitative. The results of qualitative research itself emphasize more on meaning than generalization. The data collection method used uses primary data sources and secondary data sources, Arifin (2012:141) explains that the descriptive qualitative approach is an approach that is holistic and intact. Primary data sources include observation, interviews, documentation, and triangulation. The informants of this study were students of the guidance and counseling study program in the third semester of 2017 students in the 2018/2019 academic year. The data analysis technique in this research is in the form of descriptive, descriptive research intends to explore and clarify a phenomenon or social reality by describing a variable relating to the unit or variable being studied.

IV. Results and Discussion

The content mastery service which is carried out for the third semester students of the guidance and

counseling study program is carried out in seven stages, the seven stages last for seven weeks. These stages are carried out as follows:

Table 1. Content Mastery Service Plan

No	Activity	Material	Place	Time
1.	Class Agreement	Self-confidence scale instrument filling	Classroom	60 minutes
2.	Action 1	a. Get acquainted with group members b. Provision of content mastery services c. Identify and introduce problems d. Clarifying the problem e. Interpreting the problem	Classroom	60 minutes
3.	Action 2	a. Analyze the problem b. Choose the problem to be solved first	Classroom	60 minutes
4.	Action 3	a. Setting sessions/action limits b. Reaffirming the problem c. Getting closer to a problematic situation	Classroom	60 minutes
5.	Action 4	a. Starting content mastery service b. Strengthen content mastery services	Classroom	60 minutes
6.	Action 5	a. Reviewing the cast	Classroom	60 minutes

		(events, positions, reality) b. Discuss the main focuses c. Developing further roles		
7.	Reflection	Self-confidence reflection instrument filling	Classroom	60 minutes

It is known that before being given content mastery services regarding the description of the third semester student's self-confidence, they were in the sufficient category with a percentage of 16.6% with 2 students and the poor category with a percentage of 83.3% with a total of 12 students.

Table 2. Average Class Agreement Initial Confidence per Indicator

Indicator	Material	Percentage/Criteria
1)	Confidence in your ability to complete college assignments without looking at your friends' answers	51% (Enough)
2)	Confidence to admit mistakes that have been made.	45% (Poor)
3)	Cultivate an optimistic attitude so as not to be late for class.	43% (Poor)
4)	Able to carry out tasks with confidence in their own abilities.	56% (Enough)
5)	Understand the shortcomings and accept it well	48% (Poor)
6)	Believe that by apologizing in advance will improve the situation.	57% (Enough)

The table above explains that the self-confidence before the content mastery service acts in third semester students with a percentage of 54% with sufficient criteria. This is due to various reasons, either because students are new to the campus environment or even for the first time to the capital city of Jakarta, so this makes it difficult for students to adapt to the new environment on campus. Before experiencing the action, it was also found that students had difficulty apologizing and correcting themselves from mistakes, this could be because students were still reluctant and not used to apologizing when they were wrong. So it is not uncommon for some children in the class to complain that the student has communication problems because his friend does not apologize when he does something bad, while other students feel that the actions taken by their friends are normal. Some rules, norms, cultures and habits that are different from students certainly affect the pattern of students in socializing in class. Some students also experience delays in coming to class, with various explanations given such as traffic jams,

waking up late or even online motorcycle taxis that pick up late.

Table 3. Average Student Self-Confidence Reflection Results per Indicator

Indicator	Material	Percentage/Criteria
1.	Confidence in your ability to complete college assignments without looking at your friends' answers	59% (Enough)
2.	Confidence to admit mistakes that have been made.	73% (Good)
3.	Cultivate an optimistic attitude so as not to be late for class.	81% (Very good)
4.	Able to carry out tasks with confidence in their own abilities.	68% (Good)
5.	Understand the shortcomings and accept it well	63% (Good)
6.	Believe that by apologizing in advance will improve the situation.	71% (Good)

After experiencing action in the form of content mastery services, semester III students experienced an increase in the percentage on each indicator. On the indicator of confidence in the ability to complete college assignments without seeing friends' answers, they are confident in admitting mistakes that have been made. In this indicator, after experiencing content service actions, students' self-confidence increased to 74%, a 20% increase was experienced by students after being given understanding, playing drama with other students and trying to play their roles well, this certainly helps students to be able to empathize with what other people feel. if you are in that position. So they try to build the confidence to admit what they did wrong. Improvements also occurred in indicators of fostering an optimistic attitude so that you are not late for class, being able to do assignments by believing in your own abilities, understanding shortcomings and accepting with joy, believing that by asking. After experiencing content mastery services, students experienced a very good increase in behavior from 54% to 81%. Researchers as academic supervisors provide explanations about the impact of indiscipline in time, such as late class attendance that some students do or students' delays in collecting lecture assignments.

Content mastery services carried out by students in the context of content service activities are also going well. So that some students who are lazy to attend lectures in several courses, start to get excited again, by rebuilding students' self-confidence. Self-confidence that grows back in students is very helpful for students in lecture activities, including socializing in class. The self-confidence that grows through content mastery services makes students feel that they are valuable and dare to have good communication with anyone. In addition to having self-confidence, students are also happy because they have been able to become someone who is able to adapt to every situation and can achieve everything they want. The self-confidence that exists in students makes students feel comfortable in every situation in the classroom, always ready to face new environments and new conditions and considers challenges as consequences that arise from the decisions that have been chosen.

V. Conclusion

Through this study, it was found that through content mastery services for third semester guidance and counseling students, that before experiencing content mastery services, students' self-confidence was in the sufficient category, this was seen in the indicators of confidence in their ability to complete college assignments without seeing friends' answers and being confident. admit mistakes that have been made with a value of 54% and increase to 74%. While the indicators foster an optimistic attitude so that they are not late for class, are able to do assignments with confidence in their own abilities, understand shortcomings and accept with joy, believe that by apologizing first will improve the situation from 54% to 81%. After experiencing the content mastery service, the third semester students experienced a significant increase in self-confidence. It can be concluded that the efforts made to increase self-confidence through content mastery services can significantly increase student confidence.

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